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1. OBJECTIVE OF TASK 9A

This task was designed around one of the main pillar for the management of *Xylella*-induced diseases: the control of the population of the insect vectors. The outcome of this task along with the results gathered in work-package 7 (tools and strategy to counteract the bacterium in the host plants) will help to provide useful insights for the mitigation/reduction of the impact of the infections in those areas where bacterial infections are persistent and entrenched in the territory.

Because there is still no known way of eliminating the bacterium from a diseased plant in field conditions, reducing the effectiveness of the spread mediated by the vectors remains one of the most effective means. Due to the very wide host range and the high number of potentially competent insect vectors, containment of *X. fastidiosa* infections requires integrated and combined control options (use of tolerant/resistant germplasm, vector management, vegetation management, nursery production under exclusion conditions, glasshouse or screenhouse). One of the critical points for setting adequate vector control strategies is an in depth knowledge of the biology and ecology of the insect species vectoring the bacterium in the outbreaks/epidemics. This was extremely important under the European scenario, considering the lack of knowledge on any of the “ecological” factors contributing to the emergence of the infections in Europe.

As more biological information were gathered in work-package 5, more targeted experiments could be designed in the framework of this task 9a: testing the use of non-host species for reducing the density of the juveniles; assessing the best options for controlling the adults in relation to the population dynamics in olive orchards; identifying active compounds effective for the juveniles and/or for the adults; assess if the use of “resistant” germplasm could contribute to reduce the pressure of inoculum in the environment, and thus the severe outcomes of the infections in olive groves.

Because the majority of the experiments implied the use of the infective insect specimens, these were carried out in the so called demarcated infected area of Apulia (Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2015/789 of 18 May 2015), and more specifically experimental plots and sites were located far from the border (south) of the containment area. Whereas, field surveys for defining

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the host preference, the occurrence of the different vector species and the population dynamics were conducted in the different demarcated areas as well as in the *Xylella*-free area, being not necessary to manipulate or move any infective or potentially infective specimen.

2. DESCRIPTION OF DELIVERABLE 9a

This deliverable includes the description of the overall results gathered from the field experiments conducted in the *Xylella*-demarcated areas of Apulia region (southern Italy) and aiming at reducing the vector populations.

The different experimental approaches explored for the control of the vectors can be summarized as follows:

- Evaluation of the host preference of the immature spittlebugs under the most common ecological conditions of the infected area of the Apulia (i.e. in olive groves under different management).
- Description of the adult population dynamics in olive groves to identify the best period for the application of control measures against the adults;
- Testing under field conditions different soil management techniques for the control of spittlebug nymphs in olive groves;
- Testing under field conditions different formulations for the control of the juveniles and adults;
- Assess vector-transmission efficiency using resistant and susceptible olive trees;
- Development of a lattice model to manage the vector and the infection in olive trees.

Combined with the field surveys aimed at addressing the host preference and the population dynamics, search for potential parasitoids (either in eggs or larvae) were also carried out but with poor or inconclusive results. The high density of the spittlebug populations recorded in the area also suggested that no effective “enemies” have been selected throughout the time under natural field conditions, given that this species is indigenous.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Surveys for host plant selection

Field surveys were carried out using two different sampling methods:

- 1) randomized plant sampling, consisting in the examination of about 100 individual plants per each of the most common plant genera found in the different olive orchards (range 8–24 plant genera per olive grove), looking for spittle masses of *Philaenus spumarius* nymph;
- 2) quadrats sampling, consisting in visual counting of spittlebug nymphs, both *P. spumarius* and *Neophilaenus campestris*, in 12 sample units (1 m² each) randomly distributed along the two diagonals of olive orchards.

During the first survey campaign, 9 olive groves were surveyed for 3-4 times during spring (from late March to early May).

Whereas, during the second year, a larger campaign was conducted, including more than 40 olive groves sampled only once during March–April.

During each survey, plants were identified at the genus level according to Pignatti (1997) and checked for the presence of spittles, and all plants carrying at least one spittle were considered infested.

The data collected within these surveys provided hints for setting specific experiments (see paragraph 3.2) targeting the management of the ground vegetation to suppress juveniles and therefore to lower the adult populations responsible for the transmission of the bacterium from olive to olive.

3.2 - Ground vegetation management for the control of nymphs in olive groves

For three consecutive years (2017 – 2019) different soil management techniques were compared in randomized parcels of approx. 1,500 square meters:

- (i) natural and undisturbed ground vegetation;

- (ii) soil tillage performed twice (in early winter and in spring when the majority of the nymphs were at the 4th instar);
- (iii) soil tillage performed only in winter;
- (iv) sowing *Lolium* spp;
- (v) sowing *Hordeum vulgare*.

In each parcel, 15 subplots of 0.25 square meters randomly distributed were surveyed by counting the number of spittle/plants and number of specimens (*P. spumarius* and *N. campestris*)/spittle.

An additional comparative trial was carried out in 2019 using additional management approaches:

- (i) natural and undisturbed ground vegetation;
- (ii) soil tillage performed twice (in early winter and in spring when the majority of the nymphs were at the IV instar);
- (iii) shallow ploughing
- (iv) application of mineral oil in February (to verify its effect against eggs)
- (v) application of the herbicides glyphosate (in February) and perlargonic acid (when the majority of the nymphs were at the IV instar);
- (vi) pyroweeding (when the majority of the nymphs were at the IV instar);
- (vii) mulching (when the majority of the nymphs were at the IV instar);

In this case, each treatment included 4 replicated parcels of 30 square meters, and number of spittle and specimens/spittle were recorded in 5 quadrats/parcel of 0.25 square meters.

3.3. Population dynamics and infectivity of spittlebugs in olive groves located in the Xylella-infected area of Apulia (southern Italy)

Six different olive groves were selected in the demarcated “infected area” of Apulia and monitored every two weeks, from April to October of two consecutive years (2016 and 2017), for

the presence and occurrence of spittlebugs (adults). Surveys were carried out by performing a pre-fixed number of sweeps on the ground vegetation, on olive canopies and on border plants (mainly *Myrtus* sp., *Pistacia lentiscus* and *Cupressus* sp.). More specifically, in each selected orchard sampling units consisted of 20 olive trees with 10 sweeps for each olive canopy; 30 sites for sweeping on the ground vegetation with 4 sweeps for each sites; and 10 sites for the border plants with 4 sweeps for each sites.

Insects were separated according to the species, counted and kept in ethanol prior to be tested for the presence of *X. fastidiosa* by qPCR. At each date of collection all the individuals collected, up to a maximum of 20 individuals per vegetation compartment (olive trees, ground vegetation, border plants), were subjected to diagnostic test and the % of *Xylella*-positive insects for each species estimated on a monthly basis.

3.4 Testing under field conditions different formulations for the control of spittlebugs

3.4.1 Control of juveniles

The efficacy of different insecticides, natural or inert substances (sweet orange essential oil, kaolin, zeolite) and synthetic products (deltamethrin, buprofenzin, imidacloprid) was tested to control the juvenile stages of *P. spumarius*. From 2015 to 2017, three field trials (A, B, C) were carried out within olive groves with high level of wild ground vegetation (with predominance of plant species of the family *Asteraceae* and *Leguminosae*) and abundance of spittle. For all products tested, a single application was applied at the peak of the fourth instar nymph, except for trial C, where treatments included both single and double applications of all tested products, with a 3-day interval in the case of the two applications. Briefly, in each olive grove, a surface (plot) of 20 m² in four replicates, was sprayed by using a water volume of 1,500 L/ha, then to determine the effects of each application, surveys were conducted at 3 and 7 days after treatment (DAT). Number of spittle and specimens (nymphs) were counted and recorded per unit; with a unit corresponding to a subplot of 1 m², and 4 to 8 subplots selected within each replicate of 20m².

3.4.2 Control of adults

From 2015 to 2017, six different field trials (A, B, C, D, E, F) were conducted using a randomized block with six replicates per treatment including the untreated check and neonicotinoids as reference products with known efficacy against other Auchenorrhyncha. Each replicate consisted of a single olive branch confined in a net cage where a fixed number of adult spittlebugs (collected by sweeping net) were introduced before and after the insecticides applications.

Applications were performed by spraying the entire canopy, using a water volume of 1,500 L/ha, except for the treatments with Prev-AM in trial D (Table 4), for which this volume was also increased to 2,000L/ha. In addition, in trial F the formulations containing dimethoate and imidacloprid were applied also by injections in the branches.

Adult spittlebugs were collected by sweeping net and a fixed number introduced in the cages before and after the insecticide applications.

The efficacy and persistence of each application was determined by scoring spittlebug mortality at 3, 7, 10, 15 days after treatment (DAT) for the trials conducted in 2015, and up to 20 and 25-DAT in trials conducted in 2016 and 2017.

3.5. Assessment of the vector-transmission rate from resistant olive cultivars by *Philaenus spumarius*

Three independent transmission tests were carried out in 2016 (in June, July and September) under semi-field conditions using as source plants, for the bacterial acquisition, naturally infected trees located in two olive groves in the province of Lecce (Apulia, southern Italy). In each field, infected olive trees belonged to both, susceptible and resistant cultivars. More specifically, susceptible trees were selected within those belonging to the cultivars Cellina di Nardò and Ogliarola salentina, whereas resistant trees belonged to the cultivar Leccino. Field “1” consisted of ca. 30-years old olive trees of cv Ogliarola salentina and Leccino; the trees of Ogliarola showed severe phenomenon of desiccation and decline, whereas the trees of Leccino showed only mild and scattered desiccation on few branches. Field 2 consisted of a new plantation,

realized in 2015, and although plants were infected, none showed symptoms when the experiments of acquisition were performed.

The presence of the bacterium and its concentration in the selected source plants were determined, prior each transmission experiment, through quantitative PCR assay (Harper et al., 2010).

Adults of *P. spumarius* were collected by sweeping net in the pathogen-free area and caged on the branches of the selected source plants (group of 20-30 for cage) for an acquisition access period (AAP) of 3-4 days. The insects that survived the AAP were transferred in groups of five specimens in cages with a single recipient plant, i.e. potted olive seedlings, for an inoculation access period (IAP) of 3-4 days. After the IAP the insects were recovered (both dead and alive), stored in ethanol 80% and then individually tested by qPCR. Plants were treated with a systemic insecticide and stored in an insect-proof greenhouse. A total of 122 olive seedlings were used as recipient plants (30-40 cm height) as well as three periwinkle as positive control and four olive plants as negative control. The transmission rate was then determined by testing in qPCR assays the recipient plants 12 months after the IAP.

3.6 A lattice model to manage the vector and the infection of the *Xylella fastidiosa* on olive trees

A quantitative lattice model for the infection spreading in olive orchard was constructed as a square lattice, with olive trees and herbaceous vegetation distributed on the lattice sites in a realistic way. Adult vectors were depicted as particles moving on the lattice according to specific rules dictated by the vector life cycle and feeding preferences during the year. The properties of the model are studied using numerical simulations. We performed 100 independent realizations of each experiment with different random generators. The simulated data, and their errors, are evaluated respectively as mean values and standard deviations over the independent processes. Although the data are in general plotted for a smaller period, the simulations are done for an interval of 10 years

In the model, transmission on an olive orchard are simulated setting the worst-case scenario (low efficacy of the control measures) and thus high rate of bacterial spread. The model was generated for two different scenarios: in greenhouse/nursery under confined conditions and in open field. Under these conditions we studied the effectiveness of adult control actions through the analysis of the way in which the transmission depends on (1) spacing among trees; (2) number, frequency, intensity and kind of control actions; (3) vector mobility, adopting the worst-case scenario.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Assessment of the host selection

The surveys carried out in 2015 and 2016 included 90 unique genera of herbaceous plants, for a total of 145,821 examined plants and 8,619 infested plants (overall infestation rate 5.9%), belonging to 72 different genera. The botanic families presenting the highest number of plants infested by *P. spumarius* nymphs were Asteraceae (3,319 infested plants; 38.51% of total infested plants), Fabaceae (2,423; 28.11%), Apiaceae (760; 8.82%), and Poaceae (383; 4.44%). *Sonchus* was the plant genus presenting the highest number of infested plants by *P. spumarius* nymphs. In the 2015 quadrats sampling, *Sonchus* was the prevalent host plant of meadow spittlebug, with an average infestation rate of 44%, and representing almost 21% of the total infested plants. Also, during the 2015 plants sampling, *Sonchus* was the plant genus with the highest mean percentage of total infested plants (14.3%), followed by *Knautia* (11.4%).

The 2016 plants samplings involved a much higher number of olive groves, with different plant composition and environmental conditions, and therefore showed a greater variety in the most infested plant genera. Actually, over the 42 olive groves, *Vicia*, *Medicago*, and *Knautia* presented mean infestation rates similar to the one registered for *Sonchus*. Taking into consideration all the plant genera sampled across the three surveys, some relatively uncommon plants (i.e., not included in the 25 most common plant taxa) showed very high rates of infestation, sometimes higher than *Sonchus*, e.g., *Foeniculum* (23%), *Lathyrus* (23%), *Galactites* (21%), and *Rosmarinus* (15%).

Some common plant genera appeared to be negatively selected, or avoided, by spittlebugs. Several Poaceae, Lysimachia, Raphanus, Papaver, Fumaria, Geranium, and Sherardia presented significantly lower values of infestation (Table 1).

Neophilaenus spp. nymphs were sampled and identified only during the 2015 quadrats survey, with a total of 267 nymphs sampled that accounted for 9.97% of the total spittlebug population. Poaceae were by far the most selected host plants, with 94.01% of total *Neophilaenus* spp. nymphs located on plants belonging to this family. In detail, Avena was the plant genera on which most of the nymphs were found (52.81% of the total nymphs), followed by Hordeum (16.1%), Lolium (15.36%), and Dactylis (5.99%). Host plants belonging to other families were seldom selected, with only seven *Neophilaenus* spp. nymphs sampled on forbs throughout the season.

Tab. 1: No. of sampled individual plants, no. of plants infested by *P. spumarius* and percentage (mean \pm SE) of plants infested of top 25 plant genera sampled during 2015-2016 spittlebugs surveys in Apulian olive orchards. Plant genera are ranked in descending order based on total infested plants sampled across the three surveys.

Genus/taxon	Plant family	Quadrats sampling 2015			Plants sampling 2015			Plants sampling 2016		
		Sampled plants (olive groves)	Infested plants	% infested plants (Mean \pm SE)	Sampled plants (olive groves)	Infested plants	% infested plants (Mean \pm SE)	Sampled plants (olive groves)	Infested plants	% infested plants (Mean \pm SE)
<i>Sonchus</i>	Asteraceae	629 (3)	345	44.3 \pm 17.5	1885 (5)	456	24.3 \pm 1.5	3278 (34)	404	11.9 \pm 3.4
<i>Medicago</i>	Fabaceae	1250 (3)	69	8.8 \pm 3.9	1608 (5)	167	10.3 \pm 3.8	2659 (27)	346	12.7 \pm 4.1
<i>Daucus</i>	Apiaceae	246 (2)	25	9.7 \pm 1.5	2048 (6)	289	12.0 \pm 4.9	1749 (18)	184	10.2 \pm 4.6
<i>Vicia</i>	Fabaceae	465 (3)	23	5.3 \pm 3.3	987 (5)	124	11.5 \pm 4.0	1483 (16)	343	21.7 \pm 9.7
<i>Glebionis</i>	Asteraceae	47 (2)	16	18.2 \pm 18.2	745 (2)	103	10.2 \pm 9.7	2376 (24)	270	10.9 \pm 4.2
<i>Crepis</i>	Asteraceae	1283 (3)	185	18.5 \pm 4.2	763 (2)	122	20.9 \pm 13.9	1724 (18)	79	4.0 \pm 1.9
<i>Knautia</i>	Caprifoliaceae	48 (1)	14	29.2 \pm 0.0	633 (2)	154	24.6 \pm 0.4	1441 (13)	210	13.8 \pm 4.4
<i>Melilotus</i>	Fabaceae	583 (2)	12	1.9 \pm 0.3	1573 (5)	173	11.5 \pm 4.6	2136 (21)	169	7.9 \pm 3.0
<i>Trifolium</i>	Fabaceae	397 (3)	17	4.3 \pm 2.7	2011 (6)	160	8.9 \pm 3.6	2775 (28)	142	5.2 \pm 1.4
<i>Picris</i>	Asteraceae	739 (3)	51	7.9 \pm 3.5	1175 (4)	134	18.8 \pm 7.6	1626 (17)	114	7.1 \pm 3.2
<i>Lotus</i>	Fabaceae	1526 (2)	73	3.0 \pm 2.6	920 (4)	148	13.6 \pm 4.4	2152 (23)	56	2.6 \pm 1.1
<i>Sherardia</i>	Rubiaceae	5777 (3)	186	5.4 \pm 2.5	678 (4)	48	20.0 \pm 15.5	1641 (16)	15	0.8 \pm 0.4
<i>Carduus</i>	Asteraceae	–	–	–	1230 (5)	142	10.3 \pm 3.3	1775 (23)	93	5.5 \pm 2.2
<i>Avena</i>	Poaceae	3529 (3)	83	4.5 \pm 2.3	1817 (5)	98	5.7 \pm 1.6	–	–	–
<i>Malva</i>	Malvaceae	25 (2)	6	23.6 \pm 1.4	936 (3)	76	7.9 \pm 3.9	2071 (22)	81	4.9 \pm 2.5

<i>Calendula</i>	Asteraceae	21	(2)	2	10. ₁ ± 2.4	807	(4)	27	4.4 ± 0.9	1776	(18)	84	5.2 ± 2.3
Poaceae spp.	Poaceae	2480	(2)	10	0.3 ± 0.3	–	–	–	–	1460	(15)	82	5.5 ± 1.7
<i>Lolium</i>	Poaceae	8370	(3)	16	0.2 ± 0.1	1342	(4)	70	10. ₀ ± 8.2	–	–	–	–
<i>Plantago</i>	Plantaginaceae	245	(3)	8	3.6 ± 2.2	658	(2)	54	11. ₆ ± 4.6	1100	(12)	10	0.8 ± 0.8
<i>Geranium</i>	Geraniaceae	592	(3)	16	3.4 ± 1.6	427	(3)	12	3.7 ± 3.1	1480	(15)	8	0.5 ± 0.3
<i>Myagrurum</i>	Brassicaceae	–	–	–	–	775	(3)	30	3.6 ± 1.2	1208	(12)	3	0.2 ± 0.2
<i>Hordeum</i>	Poaceae	1830	(3)	7	0.1 ± 0.1	629	(3)	15	3.7 ± 3.4	–	–	–	–
<i>Lysimachia</i>	Primulaceae	342	(3)	3	1.4 ± 0.7	920	(4)	5	0.4 ± 0.2	1100	(11)	2	0.2 ± 0.2
<i>Dactylis</i>	Poaceae	4264	(1)	2	0.0 ± 0.0	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
<i>Papaver</i>	Papaveraceae	182	(2)	0	0.0 ± 0.0	2445	(25)	1	0.0 ± 0.0	–	–	–	–

4.2 Ground vegetation management for the control of juveniles in olive groves

The experiments carried out between 2017 and 2018, showed that almost all treatments were effective in the suppressing the juveniles of *P. spumarius*, except soil tillage performed only in the winter (ANOVA: 2017: $F=18.49$; $p<0.00001$; 2018: $F=11.2401$; $p<0.00001$), while in 2019 only a double soil tillage were higher effective as compared the others treatment (ANOVA: $F=3.7581$; $p=0.1180$). In particularly, the mean number of *P. spumarius* juveniles/m² in soil tilled two times (2017: 0.1; 2018: 5.9; 2019: 0.0) was very low as compared to natural and undisturbed soil (2017: 38; 2018: 22.8; 2019: 78). No difference was recorded when soil tillage was performed only in winter (mean number of Jv: 2017: 34.1; 2018: 37.3; 2019: 36.0). Sowing in winter *Lolium* spp. (mean number of Jv: 2017: 15.5; 2018: 3.7; 2019: 40.8) generally appeared more effective than sowing *Hordeum vulgare* (mean number of Jv: 2017: 23.1; 2018: 7.2; 2019: 44.0) in reducing *P. spumarius* juvenile populations; reduction was more prominent in 2018, following two consecutive years of sowing these species (negatively selected by *P. spumarius*). For *N. campestris*, in 2017 and 2019, all treatment appeared mostly effective in reduction juvenile's population (ANOVA: 2017: $F=10.0644$; $p<0.00001$; 2019: $F=10.9902$; $p<0.00001$) as compared to uncontrolled soil (mean number of Jv/m²: 2017: 8.9; 2019: 159.6). During these experiments, double soil tillage were the best methods and completely eliminating all individual in each plot. Single soil tillage (mean number of Jv: 2017: 2.0; 2019: 18.8) and parcels sowed with both *Poaceae* (mean number of Jv/m²: *Lolium*: 2017: 3.7; 2019: 29.4; *Hordeum vulgare*: 2017: 1.2; 2019: 21.6) also significantly reduce juveniles population as compared to untreated soil. Conversely, for the trials conducted in 2018 ($F: 12.1878$; $p<0.00001$) the incidence of immatures was higher in the *Poaceae*-seeded parcels (*Lolium*: 25.9; *Hordeum vulgare*: 39.7) than in the undisturbed parcels (average number of Jv/m²: 14.0). It has to be remarked that in 2017 and 2018 the trials were conducted in the same field, whereas in 2019 the comparative trials were set in a new selected olive orchard. Thus, the discrepancy in the results, may be explained with the fact that while during the first year the seeding operations caused a disturbance in the egg

hatching of *N. campestris*, the presence of these preferred hosts may have then attracted more adults for oviposition, resulting in an increase of the populations in the following year (2018).

The comparative trials set in 2019, extended these treatments to the use of herbicides, pyroweeding and use of mineral oil for suppression of the eggs.

The data collected upon one season of treatments (Fig. 4-5) confirmed that soil tillage performed when the majority of the nymphs are in the fourth instar development stage, remains the most effective strategy to suppress juvenile, almost to zero, of both spittlebugs. Nevertheless, low number of juveniles/025 m² was also recorded following herbicide or pyroweeding applications, as well as mulching or plough at shallow depth (Fig. 4-5).

These data while support the effectiveness of mechanical interventions to suppress spittlebug nymphs, provide some information on alternative strategies that can be used, eventually in combination, for suppressing the juvenile populations, particularly in those situations where access to the site for mechanical interventions is difficult.

Figure 1. Effects of different ground vegetation management determined for two consecutive years (2017-2018) in the same plot, against juveniles of *Philaenus spumarius* compared to the undisturbed ground vegetation.

Figure 2. Effects of different ground vegetation management determined for two consecutive years (2017-2018) in the same plot, against juveniles of *Neophilaenus campestris* compared to the undisturbed ground vegetation.

Figure 3. Effects of different ground vegetation management determined upon 1 year (2019) of application against juveniles of *Philaenus spumarius* and *Neophilaenus campestris* compared to the undisturbed ground vegetation.

Figure 4. Effect of different treatments upon 1 year (2019) of application against juveniles of *Philaenus spumarius* compared to the undisturbed ground vegetation.

Figure 5. Effects of different treatments upon 1 year (2019) of application against juveniles of *Neophilaenus campestris* compared to the undisturbed ground vegetation.

4.3. Population dynamics and infectivity of spittlebug in olive groves located in the *Xylella*-infected area of Apulia (southern Italy)

Although differences in the population density were recorded between *P. spumarius* and *N. campestris*, a similar trend was observed for both species during the two consecutive years (Fig. 6). Adults of both species appeared in late April when they were collected mainly on the ground vegetation, reaching in general a peak in May and then a constant reduction till the end of the season in October.

Figure 6. Population abundance of *Philaenus spumarius* and *Neophilaenus campestris* in the infected olive groves monitored in 2016 and 2017.

P. spumarius. Regardless the vegetation compartment, a peak of adults was recorded in May reaching the following average values: on ground vegetation 4.4 specimens/sweep in 2016 and 5.4 specimens/sweep in 2017; on olive canopies 4.5 specimens/sweep in 2016 and 2.6 specimens/sweep in 2017; on border plants 5.4 specimens/sweep in 2016 and 6.7 specimens/sweep

in 2017. Following this peak, in June, the population started to decrease, particularly on the ground vegetation (drying during summer), with the majority of insects being collected on border plants. In 2016 the number of adults collected on the ground vegetation started to increase again in late August, following a rainfall period that promoted the germination of several weeds species; conversely in 2017 when the summer season was very dry, a notable increase in the number of individuals collected on ground vegetation was registered in October ($F=13.57$; $d=5$; $p<0.0001$). The overall number of adults collected from olive trees in 2017 was lower than in 2016, probably because of desiccation of olive foliage as a consequence of *X. fastidiosa* infection.

For both years, the first *Xylella*-positive individuals of *P. spumarius* were detected in May, when adults peaked on olive trees (Fig. 7), and a peak of infected specimens was always detected in June (reaching 50%), soon after the movement of the adults from the ground vegetation to the olive canopies. In 2016 the incidence of positive *P. spumarius* captured on olive trees remained substantially constant from June to October. In 2017, after the peak of positive samples recorded in June, the incidence of infected specimens decreased rapidly from July to August, and slightly increased at the end of the season (20.5%) in September. On border plants, upon the first detection of positive individuals in May (2016: 6.0%; 2017: 4.0%), a trend with a continuous increase was recorded afterwards, with a peak at the end of the season (2016: 46.2%; 2017: 23.2%). Few *P. spumarius* adults collected from the ground vegetation tested positive for the bacterium in May (2016: 3,8%; 2017: 2,5%), then their proportion sharply increased in August (2016) and at the end of September/October (2017), when adults move from the olive canopies to the newly emerged weeds.

Figure 7. Occurrence of *Xylella*-positive individuals of *Philaeus spumarius* and *Neophilaenus campestris* on infected olive canopies, ground vegetation and border plants, over the two years of surveys.

N. campestris. During both years, the population densities were consistently lower than those recorded for *P. spumarius*, regardless the monitored compartment and similarly, the occurrence of *Xf*-positive individuals of *N. campestris* was consistently lower than *P. spumarius*.

4.4 Testing under field conditions different formulations for the control of spittlebugs

4.4.1 Control of juveniles

The neonicotinoid (Confidor 200 O-Teq) and pyrethroid (Decis Evo) insecticides showed the highest efficacy (100%) at DAT3, since no nymphs survived on the sprayed vegetation (Tables 2-4).

The remaining products significantly reduced the number of nymphs and spittle, compared to the untreated check, with more prominent effect at DAT7. Among them, the best efficacy was recorded for kaolin and Prev AM (sweet orange essential oil) followed by the application of zeolite. Application of buprofenzin showed less efficacy compared to the neonicotinoids, showing similar results compared to the natural substances.

For the products tested in trial C, no significant improvements of the efficacy of the treatments was recorded upon the double applications (Table 4).

These results provided strong data that several formulations of insecticides and natural products applied to host vegetation can suppress nymphal populations of *P. spumarius*. These products can be applied to reduce juvenile MS populations in areas where mechanical control of weeds and ground vegetation is difficult to conduct. Therefore, these applications can be used to maximize an integrated strategy of control for reducing the number of adults that transmit *X. fastidiosa* to olive trees in *Xylella*-infected areas or where outbreak(s) are detected.

Table 2. Immatures mortality recorded in trial A conducted in 2015.

Treatment/ formulation	Rate (gr or mL/ha)	Trial A - 2015					
		Number of spittle/m ²			Number of nymphs/m ²		
		Before application	DAT ₃	DAT ₇	Before application	DAT ₃	DAT ₇
Untreated check	-	18.1 a	26.8 a	17.0 a	37.6 a	59.0 a	34.8 a
Decis Evo	800	15.3 a	0.1 b	0.1 b	24.5 a	0.3 b	0.1 c
Applaud Plus	1,500	17.1 a	27.0 a	15.3 a	38.8 a	43.6 a	23.4 ab
Kaolin	40,000	18.9 a	19.0 a	11.5 a	30.8 a	31.6 a	16.9 b
Zeolite	6,000	16.1 a	20.6 a	12.8 a	26.5 a	36.0 a	27.3 ab
<i>F value</i>		0.25	6.06	5.14	1	6.89	10.12
<i>Pr>F</i>		0.9325	0.0004	0.0012	0.4321	0.0001	<.00001

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

Table 3. Immatures mortality recorded in trial A conducted in 2016.

Treatment/ formulation	Trial B - 2016						
	Rate (gr or mL/h a)	Number of spittle/m ²			Number of nymphs/m ²		
		Before applicati on	DAT ₃	DAT ₇	Before application	DAT ₃	DAT ₇
Untreated check	-	48.8 a	69.2 a	60.4 a	136.8 a	236.8 a	152.0 a
Decis Evo	800	44.8 a	0.4 c	0.0 d	154.4 a	1.2 c	0.4 d
Confidor 200	1,120	43.2 a	4.8 c	1.2 d	94.0 a	17.6 c	1.2 d
Applaud Plus	1,500	39.6 a	60.0 a	24.0 c	94.8 a	151.2 ab	40.8 c
Kaolin	40,000	39.2 a	36.0 b	27.2 c	131.2 a	147.2 ab	54.0 c
Zeolite	6,000	38.0 a	45.6 b	38.8 b	132.8 a	141.2 ab	113.2 b
PREV-AM	8,000	50.0 a	46.8 b	31.6 bc	132.0 a	112.0 b	72.0 c
<i>F value</i>		<i>0.84</i>	<i>31.54</i>	<i>30.54</i>	<i>0.92</i>	<i>5.02</i>	<i>14.75</i>
<i>Pr>F</i>		0.5381	<.00001	<.00001	0.7395	<.00001	<.00001

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

Table 4.

Trial C - 2017

Treatment/ formulation	Rate (gr or mL/h a)	Number of spittle/m ²			Number of nymphs/m ²		
		Before 1st application	DAT ₃	DAT ₇	Before 1st application	DAT ₃	DAT ₇
Untreated check	-	51.6 a	72.5 a	96.4 a	99.8 a	145.6 a	230.8 a
Confidor 200	1,120	52.4 a	31.2 c	20.4 d	82.4 a	44.0 d	26.8 d
Confidor 200*	1,120	46.4 a	23.6 c	0 d	86.8 a	34.4 d	0 d
Kaolin	40,000	56.8 a	56.8 ab	82.8 ab	100.0 a	109.6 bc	178.0 ab
Kaolin*	40,000	48.8 a	48.8 b	85.2 ab	79.2 a	85.6 c	180.8 ab
PREV-AM	8,000	44.8 a	59.6 ab	62.8 bc	78.0 a	112.4 abc	154.0 bc
PREV-AM *	8,000	59.6 a	71.2 a	54.0 c	102.4 a	128.8 ab	104.8 c
<i>F value</i>		<i>1.23</i>	<i>12.03</i>	<i>16.19</i>	<i>1.22</i>	<i>13.20</i>	<i>12.26</i>
<i>Pr>F</i>		0.2949	<.00001	<.00001	0.2966	<.00001	<.00001

*double applications

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

4.4.2 Control of adults

Synthetic pyrethroids [Decis Jet (deltamethrin) and Karathe Zeon (*lambda*-cyhalothrin)] and neonicotinoids [Epik SL (acetamiprid), Confidor 200 O-Teq (imidacloprid), Actara 25 (thiamethoxan), Luzindo WG (thiamethoxam mixed with clarantraniprole)] showed the highest efficacy causing mortality ranging from 76.7% to 100% at 3-DAT and persistence up to 15-DAT with mortality higher than 40% (Table 5-10). Applications of organophosphorus insecticides [Perfektion or Rogor L40 (dimethoate), Reldan 22 (chlorpyrifos-methyl) and Dursban 75 WG (chlorpyrifos-ethyl)] caused lower mortality rates compared to the neonicotinoids and pyrethroids, and in the case of Dursban 75 WG (chlorpyrifos-ethyl), results were inconsistent between the two years of testing. Although initial mortality was recorded for Laser (spinosad) and Prev-AM (sweet orange essential oil) used at high volume of application, both insecticides showed poor or no persistence. No dead insects were recorded for the following treatments: Movento 48 SC (spirotetramat), Teppeki (flonicamid), Plenum (pymetrozine), Applaud Plus (buprofenzin), Pyganic (natural pyrethrin) and Neemazal (azadirachtin).

Spray applications were more efficacious and rapid than injection. For example, at 3-DAT mortality rates for imidacloprid were 98.3% vs 60% , respectively, and for dimethoate were 88.3% vs 55%, respectively. Conversely, formulations applied by injection showed slightly higher persistence at 20-DAT with Confidor 200 O-Teq (imidacloprid) mortality 75.8% vs 69.4%, for injection and spray; and for Perfektion (dimethoate) mortality at 20.7 vs 8.9, respectively (Table 10).

These data on efficacy of different chemicals and formulations for the control of *P. spumarius*, showed that neonicotinoids performed better than the other products. In general, however, for the majority of the products tested low persistence was recorded. These results suggest that newer formulations and chemicals are needed along with trials to determine proper timing and number of applications for effective management of this vector. Moreover, an integrated pest management

approach is needed to manage spittlebug populations along with a sustainable strategy to reduce progression of OQDS in olive grove.

Table 5. Insect mortality recorded in trial A conducted in 2015

Treatment/formulation	Rate (gr or mL/ha)	Mortality (%) – Trial A - 2015			
		DAT ₃	DAT ₇	DAT ₁₀	DAT ₁₅
Untreated check	-	0 c	1.5 c	0 c	2.7 c
Epick SL	1,500	100 a	16.7 abc	10.5 a	17.9 ab
Confidor 200 O-Teq OD	1,125	87.2 ab	13.3 bc	8.8 ab	16.9 ab
Decis Jet EC	1,150	100 a	28.3 ab	4.3 abc	21.2 a
Karathe Zeon 1.5 CS	2,500	85 b	10.2 bc	0.7 c	16.1 ab
Trebon Up EC	500	84.4 b	34.2 a	3.1 abc	7.5 bc
Perfektion EC	2,250	6.7 c	0.9 c	2.3 bc	5.3 c
Plenum WP	800	0 c	1.3 c	0.6 c	4.7 c
Applaud Plus WP	2,000	2.8 c	1.7 c	1.1 bc	4.9 c
<i>F value</i>		<i>110.83</i>	<i>3.62</i>	<i>2.28</i>	<i>4.22</i>
<i>Pr>F</i>		<i><.00001</i>	<i>0.0030</i>	<i>0.0407</i>	<i>0.0010</i>

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

Table 6. Insect mortality recorded in trial B conducted in 2015

Treatment/formulation	Rate (gr or mL/ha)	Mortality (%) – Trial B - 2015			
		DAT ₃	DAT ₇	DAT ₁₀	DAT ₁₅
Untreated check	-	0 e	0 d	0 d	5.6 cd
Epik SL	1,500	76.7 bc	81.5 a	35.4 ab	42 a
Confidor 200 O-Teq OD	1,125	86.7 ab	81.1 a	45.2 a	47 a
Decis Jet EC	1,150	98.3 a	72.1 a	15.5 cd	15.5 bcd
Karathe Zeon 1.5 CS	2,500	85 ab	81.7 a	32.1 ab	17 bc
Trebon Up EC	500	65 c	51.6 b	39 ab	24 b
Perfektion EC	2,250	25 d	36.4 c	22.7 bc	4.6 d
Rogor L 40 SL	2,000	20 d	36.8 c	13.3 cd	6.3 cd
Plenum WP	800	0 e	0 d	0 d	4.4 d
Applaud Plus WP	2,000	0 e	0 d	0 d	5.6 cd
Movento 48 SC	3,750	0 e	0 d	0 d	6.1 cd
<i>F value</i>		<i>71.15</i>	<i>85.84</i>	<i>9.91</i>	<i>17.67</i>
<i>Pr>F</i>		<i><.00001</i>	<i><.00001</i>	<i><.00001</i>	<i><.00001</i>

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

Table 7. Insect mortality recorded in trial C conducted in 2015

Treatment/formulation	Rate (gr or mL/ha)	Mortality (%) – Trial C - 2015			
		DAT ₃	DAT ₇	DAT ₁₀	DAT ₁₅
Untreated check	-	0 c	0 b	1.1 b	1.7 b
Confidor 200 O-Teq OD	1,125	86.7 a	88.3 a	68.9 a	64.7 a
Neemazal EC	3,000	18.3 b	0 b	0 b	3.5 b
Pyganic EC	3,750	23.3 b	5.6 b	0.6 b	3.8 b
Prev AM SL	8,000	23.3 b	1.8 b	3.6 b	0 b
<i>F value</i>		44.14	317.58	79.01	17.39
<i>Pr>F</i>		<.00001	<.00001	<.00001	<.00001

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

Table 8. Insect mortality recorded in trial D conducted in 2016

Treatment/formulation	Rate (gr or mL/ha)	Mortality (%) – Trial D - 2016		
		DAT ₃	DAT ₇	DAT ₁₅
Untreated check	-	7.5 c	0 a	5 ab
Confidor 200 O-Teq OD	1,125	85.8 a	8.3 a	3.3 ab
Neemazal EC	3,000	6.7 c	5 a	7.5 a
Pyganic EC	3,750	32.5 bc	6.7 a	5 ab
Prev-AM SL (application volume of 1,500 L/ha)	8,000	30 bc	1.7 a	5.8 ab
Prev-AM SL (application volume of 2,000 L/ha)	8,000	54.2 ab	8.3 a	3.3 ab
Decis Jet EC	1,150	82.5 a	13.3 a	0 b
<i>F value</i>		<i>7.83</i>	<i>0.89</i>	<i>1.49</i>
<i>Pr>F</i>		<i><.00001</i>	<i>0.5118</i>	<i>0.2146</i>

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

Table 9. Insect mortality recorded in trial E conducted in 2016

Treatment/formulation	Rate (gr or mL/ha)	Mortality (%) – Trial E - 2016					
		DAT ₃	DAT ₇	DAT ₁₀	DAT ₁₅	DAT ₂₀	DAT ₂₅
Untreated check	-	20 b	4.6 d	4.9 d	5.2 d	5.8 b	12.1 a
Confidor 200 O-Teq OD	1,125	91.7 a	92.6 a	89.2 a	92.4 a	41.7 a	16.7 a
Movento 48 SC	3,750	26.7 b	7.4 d	1.4 d	4.7 d	5 b	11.5 a
Reldan 22 EC	4,500	66.7 a	46.2 c	18.4 c	15.3 c	4.8 b	7.6 a
Dursban 75 WG	1,050	81.7 a	66.7 b	41.9 b	32.9 b	7.5 b	18.6 a
Actara 25 WG	450	90 a	89.4 a	80.9 a	98.5 a	0 b	16.7 a
Luzindo WG	250	88.3 a	91 a	86.5 a	94.2 a	25 ab	16.7 a
Teppeki WG	140	43.3 b	12.5 d	3.9 d	1.1 d	7.2 b	12.6 a
Laser SC	450	80 a	31.2 c	10.3 cd	4 d	4.8 b	9.2 a
<i>F value</i>		12.83	40.51	149.35	232.79	2.38	0.14
<i>Pr>F</i>		<.00001	<.00001	<.00001	<.00001	0.0333	0.9966

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

Table 10. Insect mortality recorded in trial F conducted in 2017

Treatment/formulation	Rate (gr or mL/ha)	Mortality (%) – Trial F - 2017					
		DAT ₃	DAT ₇	DAT ₁₀	DAT ₁₅	DAT ₂₀	DAT ₂₅
Untreated check	-	23.3 d	8.5 e	5.6 b	11.1 d	9.1 b	5.4 b
Confidor 200 O-Teq OD	1,125	98.3 a	65.8 ab	71.4 a	73.9 b	69.4 a	8.3 b
Confidor 200 O-Teq OD - Injection	1,125	60 c	76.9 a	67.5 a	80.2 b	75.8 a	16.7 ab
Movento 48 SC	3,750	15 d	10.8 e	7.6 b	15.1 cd	6.8 b	7.4 b
Reldan 22 EC	4,500	90 ab	36.1 cd	15.4 b	17.1 cd	9.8 b	1.3 b
Dursban 75 WG	1,050	70 bc	36 cd	20.8 b	14.6 cd	14.7 b	3.8 b
Actara 25 WG	450	96.7 a	80.3 a	70.6 a	86.4 ab	66.8 a	0 b
Luzindo WG	250	98.3 a	70.5 a	77.1 a	94.4 a	59.6 a	36.1 a
Teppeki WG	140	21.7 d	10.4 e	6.9 b	6.9 d	8.3 b	2.2 b
Laser SC	450	90 ab	51.1 bc	18.6 b	10.7 d	15.8 b	4.5 b
Perfektion EC	2,250	88.3 ab	21.2 de	10.7 b	4.4 d	8.9 b	5.5 b
Perfektion EC - Injection	2,250	55 c	36.7 cd	20.9 b	28.7 c	20.7 b	9.1 b
<i>F value</i>		<i>18.87</i>	<i>24.94</i>	<i>23.94</i>	<i>57.32</i>	<i>19.41</i>	<i>17.17</i>
<i>Pr>F</i>		<i><.00001</i>	<i><.00001</i>	<i><.00001</i>	<i><.00001</i>	<i><.00001</i>	<i><.00001</i>

Mean values followed by the same letter, on the column, are not statistically different at the probability levels $p < 0.05$

4.5. Assessment of the impact of resistant olive cultivars in the transmission of *Xylella fastidiosa*

When the branches selected for the acquisition (previously identified as *Xylella*-positive trees) were tested by qPCR, an high incidence of negative branches was recorded for the trees of the cultivar Leccino, whereas the bacterium appeared to be uniformly distributed in the trees of the cultivars Ogliarola salentina and Cellina di Nardò. The quantitative diagnostic tests performed on the selected trees estimated a bacterial population in the range of 10^5 CFU/ml for the cultivar Cellina di Nardò and Ogliarola Salentina, and in the range of 10^3 CFU/ml in the leaves sampled from the cultivar Leccino. After the AAP, a general high insect mortality (ca. 40-60%) was recorded, with the highest mortality recorded in July, probably due to unfavourable high temperatures occurring in the cages prepared on the branches, with insects forced to remain in a specific position of the tree.

Diagnostic tests performed on the insects after the IAP (approx.. 500 individuals) showed a significant different rate of acquisition in relation to the source plants. qPCR-positive specimens were consistently detected upon feeding on branches of Ogliarola salentina and Cellina di Nardò, with an average of 32,4 % and a peak of acquisition recorded in July. Conversely, for Leccino the overall acquisition rate was 7.6%, with a peak of 16.7% in the month of July.

All insects recovered from the branches of the trees of Leccino testing negative for the bacterium, tested negative as well.

The efficiency of the transmission was found to be positively correlated to the acquisition rates. A higher number of *Xylella*-infected recipient plants was recovered with the insects fed on Ogliarola salentina and Cellina di Nardò than on Leccino branches. Specifically, 17 out 49 recipient plants (34.6%) tested positive upon the exposure to insects fed on the first 2 cultivars, whereas only 2 positives out 44 plants (4.5%) were recovered upon the exposure to insects fed on Leccino branches.

These results prompt for more extensive experiments now ongoing in the framework of the project XF-ACORS (727987).

4.6 A lattice model to manage the vector and the infection of the *Xylella fastidiosa* on olive trees

A lattice model was constructed to simulate the bacterium/vector/tree infection interplay under different adult control actions, considering four factors: vector infectivity, transmission efficiency, number of vectors and time they spent on the host. Our findings prove that the number of vector/tree is the most relevant parameter controlling the infection. In particular, when the asymptotic fractions of infected trees after 2 years are plotted as a function of the cumulative number of vectors per tree, in open and closed orchards, a transition is observed, from a state of low infectivity to a state of high infectivity, controlled by the cumulative number of vector/tree. Reducing this number below a certain threshold allows to hold the *Xylella* invasion within an acceptable range. Actually, in order to reproduce the vector dynamics and the resulting *X. fastidiosa* transmission in an olive orchard, the evaluation of the model parameters is crucial. While in some cases the literature comes to our aid (see for example the estimation of the number of eggs for female or the adult vector population discussed in Methods section), in other cases data are lacking, and the parameters are arbitrarily chosen (see for example the case of the vector mobility discussed in Results section). In all the unreliable cases, we choose to fix the parameters at the worst values on the point of view of the infection control, with the idea that, if the infection is controlled in the worst case, even more so, it can be controlled in the other ones. Data on the spittlebug adult habits (time spent on the host, frequency of movements from one twig to another, etc.) could improve the realism of our modelization. Considering a three-dimensional model would also go in the direction of a more realistic description. In this case we would expect an increase of the mean time spent by the vectors on the same tree, and, consequentially, a slowing-down of the infection with respect to the two-dimensional case.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The experimental activities carried out in the framework of this WP, coupled with the scientific knowledge gathered in WP5, allowed to gather the first dataset of scientific information tailored on the specific epidemiological conditions occurring in the severe *Xylella*-epidemics discovered in Europe. Such information are crucial to tackle the vector populations, in the hope of reducing the rate of transmission and spread of the bacterium, i.e. slow down the spread rate of the disease.

Olives are the predominant and the most susceptible hosts contributing to this epidemics, thus epidemiological data have been mainly developed using olive groves as experimental scenario.

The major experimental outcomes can be summarized in the following points:

- The wide polyphagy of *P. spumarius* is well known, but host plant selection and host plant preference in open field conditions have been rarely investigated using a rational approach. The surveys conducted within WP5 and WP9 investigated host plant selection under real field conditions in the olive groves rather than host plant preference determined under controlled conditions using choice tests. The knowledge of plant community of the olive grove and of host plant selection by the vector provides hints on the potential development of high populations of *P. spumarius* at specific sites, i.e. supporting pest risk assessment.
- Our surveys highlighting some clear host plant selection and avoidance by *P. spumarius* nymphs, suggesting the need of further research on this topic. In fact, due to the very high polyphagy of the meadow spittlebug, it was interesting to identify, besides the preferred plants, those species that are negatively selected. Among these latter, some Poaceae, Oxalis (Oxalidaceae), *Lysimachia* (Myrsinaceae), *Sherardia* (Rubiaceae), *Geranium* (Geraniaceae), *Papaver* (Papaveraceae), *Fumaria* (Fumariaceae), and *Raphanus*

(Brassicaceae) were avoided by *P. spumarius* nymphs (i.e., significantly less infested compared to their abundance in the sample area).

- The above information were used to set several trials for the management of the ground vegetation in olive groves for suppressing spittlebug nymphs; whose overall results indicated that soil tillage performed at the right stage of development of the nymphs remains the most effective strategy to suppress immatures and prevent the emergence of adults responsible for the bacterial spread. As such, this became one of the mandatory action to be implemented in the infected demarcated area to reduce the rate of spread of the bacterium.
- Even if not as effective as soil tillage, several other means can be used to contribute to reduce the populations of the juveniles: applications of herbicides, pyroweeding, sowing *Poaceae*, using different insecticides. Although sowing gramineous plants can favor the development of *N. campestris*, (as shown upon two years of sowing *Lolium* and *Hordeum*), this latter species (see points below) seems to be of minor importance in the disease spread in olive groves.
- The large-scale surveys for juveniles in the infected area further confirmed that *P. spumarius* is far the most abundant vector species, i.e. playing the major role in the spread of the bacterium. The maximum population level of *P. spumarius* nymphs measured in olive groves was estimated in a range of 10–40 nymphs per square meter, whereas the populations of *N. campestris* were much lower, with a peak of one to seven nymphs per square meter. Similar data were collected while monitoring adults: density on olive canopies and infectivity were far much lower for *N. campestris* than *P. spumarius*.
- As for the juveniles, it was interesting to note that higher plant infestation rates were recorded in the currently infected area compared to the north of the Apulia region. Lower populations of the vector north of the infected area may contribute to slow down the *X. fastidiosa* spread. However, these are preliminary data and they should be confirmed by ad hoc estimation of vectors' population abundances.

- Experimental data collected on the use of insecticides to suppress adult spittlebugs highlighted several drawbacks in their efficacy (low efficacy or low persistence compared to the temporal window during which adults are potentially competent vectors of the bacterium). Indeed, the results of the surveys for adults, clearly indicated that (i) in infected olive groves they can reach high rate of infectivity, (ii) populations actively move from one vegetation compartment to another (i.e. from olive canopies to border plants or ground vegetation and viceversa), making extremely difficult targeted applications of insecticides. However, the knowledge on the transmission mechanisms and the data collected on the adult's infectivity clearly suggest the need of intervention immediately after the emergence of the adults, before they are able to acquire and transmit the bacterium.
- The data collected on the transmission efficiency of the spittlebug fed on resistant olive cultivar Leccino, demonstrate that the use of resistant plants in the infected area, although harboring the bacterium, can significantly reduce the pressure of inoculum and the rate of spread in the area where the bacterium became endemic, being a valuable strategy to contain the spread of the pathogen/disease. The low bacterial concentration in the trees of cv Leccino resulted in a significant lower transmission rate (4.5% vs 34.6% in Cellina/Ogliarola). This lower transmission efficiency coupled with the erratic distribution of the bacterium in these plants, i.e. less probability than an insect visiting the trees of Leccino can acquire the bacterium, reduce the rate of the acquisition and the subsequent transmission.
- The development of a lattice model for the spread of *X. fastidiosa* in olive grove clearly shows that an appropriate vector and transmission IPM strategy, based on a few key actions with an appropriate timing can mitigate the plant pathogen invasion. In order to reduce the overall population, it is firstly necessary to apply several control actions on the immature spittlebugs, and then it is critical to decimate the adults before they acquire or at the time of their first acquisition. The egg and juvenile population management are control key points aiming at diminishing the population size by eliminating a percentage of individuals, whereas properly targeted control of the adults is necessary for minimizing the pathogen

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acquisition and transmission (mainly to reduce the secondary spread olive-to-olive). None of these actions can be disregarded to obtain the IPM functional response over the management of both the vectors and the plant pathogen invasion.

6. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

A more comprehensive description of the experimental settings and results gathered from the trials described in this deliverable, can be retrieved directly from the scientific papers published (Open Access) in the framework of the project PONTE:

1. Dongiovanni C., Altamura G., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Saponari M., Cavalieri V., 2018. Evaluation of efficacy of different insecticides against *Philaenus spumarius* L., vector of *Xylella fastidiosa* in olive orchards in Southern Italy. *Arthropod Management Pest*, 43(1): 1-4. doi: 10.1093/amt/tsy034.
2. Dongiovanni C., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Altamura G., Cavalieri V., 2018. Evaluation of insecticides for the control of juveniles of *Philaenus spumarius* L., 2015-17. *Arthropod Management Tests* 43(1): 1-2. doi: 10.1093/amt/tsy073.
3. Dongiovanni C., Cavalieri V., Bodino N., Tauro D., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Altamura G., Lasorella C., Bosco D., 2018. Plant selection and population trend of spittlebug immatures (Hemiptera: Aphrophoridae) in olive groves of the Apulia region of Italy. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 112(1): 67-74. doi: 10.1093/jee/toy289.
4. Fierro A., Liccardo A., Porcelli F., 2019. A lattice model to manage the vector and the infection of the *Xylella fastidiosa* on olive trees. *Scientific Reports*, 9: 8723.

7. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIONS

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

5. Dongiovanni C., Cavalieri V., Altamura G., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Corrado I., De Lillo E., Porcelli F., 2016. *Philaenus spumarius* L. adult vector control, expected opportunity and impact for effective IPM strategy chemical component. In: Proceedings of the XXV Italian National Congress of Entomology, Padova, Italy, 20-24 June 2016, p. 267.
6. Dongiovanni C., Cavalieri V., Altamura G., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Corrado I., Saponari M., De Lillo E., Porcelli F., 2016. Risultati preliminari di prove comparative di efficacia per il controllo di *Philaenus spumarius*, vettore di *Xylella fastidiosa*. *Atti Giornate Fitopatologiche*, 1: 393-402.
7. Dongiovanni C., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Tauro D., Ciniero A., Altamura G., Palmisano F., Cavalieri V., 2016. Field experiments for the containment of the spread of *Xylella fastidiosa* in olive orchards. In: National Congress of Phytopathological Society, Ancona, Italy, 5-7 September 2018.
8. Bodino N., Plazio E., Cavalieri V., Dongiovanni C., Ripamonti M., Volani S., Gilioli G., Fumarola G., Di Carolo M., Porcelli F., Bosco D., 2017. Host-plant association and host-shifting of nymphs and adults of *Philaenus spumarius* L. in Italian olive orchards. In: Proceedings of the 3rd Hemipteran-Plant Interactions Symposium, 4-8 June 2017, Madrid, Spain, p. 36.
9. Bodino N., Plazio E., Picciau L., Cavalieri V., Dongiovanni C., Di Carolo M., Tauro D., Volani S., Salerno M., Russo V., Porcelli F., Gilioli G., Bosco D., 2017. Phenology population dynamics and host plants of *Philaenus spumarius* in Italian olive groves. In: Proceedings of the European conference on *Xylella fastidiosa*: finding answers to a global problem, Palma de Mallorca, Spain, 13-15 November 2017, p. 19.
10. Cavalieri V., Dongiovanni C., Altamura G., Tauro D., Ciniero A., Morelli M., Bosco D., Saponari M., 2017. Evaluation of olive cultivar effect on the efficiency of the acquisition and transmission of *Xylella fastidiosa* by *Philaenus spumarius* (Hemiptera: Aphrophoridae). In: Proceedings of the 3rd Hemipteran-Plant Interactions Symposium, 4-8 June 2017, Madrid, Spain, p. 39.
11. Dongiovanni C., Cavalieri V., Altamura G., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Saponari M., Porcelli F., 2017. Preliminary results of comparative efficacy evaluation trials against *Philaenus spumarius* L., vector of *Xylella fastidiosa*. In: D'Onghia A.M. (ed.), Brunel S. (ed.), Valentini F. (ed.). *Xylella fastidiosa* & the Olive Quick Decline Syndrome (OQDS). A serious worldwide challenge for the safeguard of olive trees. Bari: CIHEAM, 2017. pp. 79-80. (Options Méditerranéennes: Série A. Séminaires

- Méditerranéens; n. 121: 79-80).
12. Dongiovanni C., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Tauro D., Cavalieri V., Altamura G., Saponari M., Porcelli F., 2017. Preliminary evaluation of different insecticides against *Philaenus spumarius*. In: Proceedings of the European conference on *Xylella fastidiosa*: finding answers to a global problem, Palma de Mallorca, Spain, 13-15 November 2017, p. 22.
 13. Dongiovanni C., Cavalieri V., Bodino N., Tauro D., Di Carolo M., Altamura G., Fumarola G., Ciniero A., Lasorella C., Bosco D., Saponari M., 2017. Host-plant preference of *Philaenus spumarius* nymphs in olive orchards of the Apulian Region of Italy. In: Proceedings of the European conference on *Xylella fastidiosa*: finding answers to a global problem, Palma de Mallorca, Spain, 13-15 November 2017, p. 51.
 14. Mezei I., Convertini S., Drei F., Tescari E., Tornè M., Cavalieri V., Dongiovanni C., Porcelli F., 2017. Isoclast™ Active as a new tool for controlling *Xylella fastidiosa* invasion via vector control. In: Proceedings of the European conference on *Xylella fastidiosa*: finding answers to a global problem, Palma de Mallorca, Spain, 13-15 November 2017, p. 58.
 15. Salerno M., Russo V., Sefa V., Lamaj F., Basher N., Verrastro V., Porcelli F., 2017. *Zelus renardii* an assassin bug candidate for *Philaenus spumarius* biocontrol. In: Proceedings of the European conference on *Xylella fastidiosa*: finding answers to a global problem, Palma de Mallorca, Spain, 13-15 November 2017, pp. 22-23.
 16. Dongiovanni C., Fumarola G., Di Carolo M., Tauro D., Ciniero A., Altamura G., Palmisano F., Silletti M.R., Pollastro P., Cavalieri V., 2018. Sputacchina dell'olivo, insetticidi a confronto. *Informatore Agrario*, 24-25, 51-56.
 17. Dongiovanni C., Altamura G., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Saponari M., Cavalieri V., 2018. Evaluation of efficacy of different insecticides against *Philaenus spumarius* L., vector of *Xylella fastidiosa* in olive orchards in Southern Italy. *Arthropod Management Pest*, 43(1): 1-4. doi: 10.1093/amt/tsy034.
 18. Acquasanta F., Bacci L., Baser N., Carmignano P.M., Cavalieri V., Cioffi M., Convertini S., D'Accolti A., Dal Maso E., Diana F., Diana L., Di Carolo M., Dongiovanni C., Facchinetti D., Fedele F., Fumarola G., Gammino R.P., Garganese F., Lamaj G., Maffioli G., Mezei I., Montecchio L., Picciotti U., Porcelli F., Russo V., Salerno M., Schiavarelli A., Sefa V., Tescari E., Verrastro V., 2018. Tradizione e innovazione nel controllo del *Philaenus spumarius* Linneaus, 1758 (Hemiptera Aphrophoridae). *Atti Giornate Fitopatologiche*, 1: 181-190.
 19. Dongiovanni C., Cavalieri V., Fumarola G., Di Carolo M., Tauro D., Ciniero A., Altamura G., Palmisano F., Silletti M.R., Pollastro P., 2018. Valutazione dell'efficacia di diversi insetticidi nei confronti degli individui adulti di *Philaenus spumarius* vettore di *Xylella fastidiosa*. *Atti Giornate Fitopatologiche*, 1: 191-200.

20. Dongiovanni C., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Altamura G., Cavalieri V., 2018. Evaluation of insecticides for the control of juveniles of *Philaenus spumarius* L., 2015-17. *Arthropod Management Tests* 43(1): 1-2. doi: 10.1093/amt/tsy073.
21. Dongiovanni C., Cavalieri V., Bodino N., Tauro D., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Altamura G., Lasorella C., Bosco D., 2018. Plant selection and population trend of spittlebug immatures (Hemiptera: Aphrophoridae) in olive groves of the Apulia region of Italy. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 112(1): 67-74. doi: 10.1093/jee/toy289.
22. Dongiovanni C., Di Carolo M., Fumarola G., Cavalieri V., Tauro D., Ciniero A., Altamura G., Saponari M., 2018. Containment measures against *Philaenus spumarius* for decreasing the spreading of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp *pauca* on olive trees in Apulia Region. In: Proceedings of XXIII National Congress of Phytopathological Society (SIPaV), Piacenza, Italy, 4-6 October 2017.
23. Dongiovanni C., Cavalieri V., Fumarola G., Di Carolo M., Ciniero A., Altamura G., Saponari M., 2018. Soil management techniques for the control of juvenile populations of spittlebugs in olive groves. In: Proceedings of 2nd Joint Annual Meeting of H2020 PONTE (Pest Organisms Threatening Europe) and XF-ACTORS (*Xylella Fastidiosa* Active Containment Through a multidisciplinary-Oriented Research Strategy) Projects. Valencia, Spain, 23-26 October 2018, p. 72.
24. Fierro A., Liccardo A., Porcelli F., 2019. A lattice model to manage the vector and the infection of the *Xylella fastidiosa* on olive trees. *Scientific Reports*, 9: 8723.

INFORMATIVE EVENTS

1. Technical Meeting organized by COLDIRETTI, 31/03/2016, Lecce, Italy. F. Porcelli (UNIBA) gave a talk on “Controllare il vettore, gestire gli oliveti, mitigare il (Co)DiRO”.
2. Technical Workshop organized by Apulian Regional Association of Agricultural Technicians and Researchers (ARPTRA), Italy, 08/04/2016, Ostuni (Brindisi), Italy. F. Porcelli (UNIBA) gave a presentation on “*Philaenus spumarius* vettore di *Xylella fastidiosa*. Biologia, comportamento e controllo integrato”. C. Dongiovanni (UNIBA) gave a presentation on “Risultati preliminari di prove comparative di efficacia per il controllo di *Philaenus spumarius*, vettore di *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* ceppo CoDiRO”.
3. International Prize BIOL (Organic extra virgin olive oil) 2017, 18/03/2017, Ostuni (Brindisi), Italy. F. Porcelli (UNIBA) on “*Xylella* e novità per l’olivicoltura biologica”.
4. Technical Fair AGRILEVANTE, Italy, 14/10/2017, Bari, Italy. F. Porcelli (UNIBA) gave a lecture on “Advances on the spittlebugs vector bionomics and control in Italy”.

5. Conference "Future Oil. *Xylella* and the future of Mediterranean food", organized by CIA, Confederation of Italian Farmers and AGIA Young Agricultural Enterprises Association, 29/10/2018, Matera, Italy. C. Dongiovanni (CRSFA) talk on “Insetti vettori di *Xylella fastidiosa* in Puglia e strategie di gestione”.
6. Foro Olivar de Ecija, 17/12/2018, Ecija, Spain. A. Fereres (CSIC) gave a talk on “Insectos vectores de *Xylella* y posibles métodos de control”.
7. Jornadas de Avances de la Sanidad Vegetal, 20/12/2018, Jaen, Spain. M. Morente (CSIC) gave a talk on “Vectores potenciales de *Xylella fastidiosa* en España. Posibles estrategias de control”.
8. Informative meeting on *Xylella fastidiosa*, organized by the operational group GAL Valle D’Itria, Italy, 15/03/2019, Martina Franca (Taranto), Italy. C. Dongiovanni (CRSFA) gave an informative lecture on vector control.
9. Informative meeting on *Xylella fastidiosa*, organized by the operational group GAL Valle D’Itria, Italy, 20/03/2019, Locorotondo (Bari), Italy. C. Dongiovanni (CRSFA) gave an informative lecture on vector control.
10. Technical conference on *Xylella fastidiosa*, organized by Instituto Juan Gil-Albert-Benissa, Spain, 21/05/2019, Alicante, Spain. A. Fereres (CSIC) gave a talk on “*Xylella fastidiosa*: avances en investigación, transmisión y estrategias de control.”